

Characterization and Safety Assessment of Nanomaterials

Dhaval J Kamothi¹, Ranjith D² and Dinesh Kumar³

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Pharmacology and Toxicology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, Bareilly, U.P., 243122

²Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Pharmacology and Toxicology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, Bareilly, U.P., 243122

³Principal Scientist & Head, Division of Pharmacology & Toxicology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, 243122, U.P, India

Introduction

The field of nanotechnology is one of the most emerging scientific areas of interest. However, little emphasis has been put on the characterization and safety evaluation of nanoparticles. The present article covers some of the important aspects of characterization and safety evaluation parameters of nanomaterials. Characterization of nanomaterials is an important aspect of nanotechnology as the particle size/hydrodynamic diameter, surface charge/zeta potential and morphology of nanomaterials highly impact the transport and interaction of the nanomaterials with the target cell or receptor. Different characterization techniques used are dynamic light scattering, zeta potential, encapsulation efficiency, X-ray diffraction study, transmission electron microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, atomic force microscopy, and spectroscopic studies such as UV-visible spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. Different safety assessment parameters such as the Proliferation assay, Apoptosis assay, Necrosis assay, Oxidative stress assay, DNA damage assay, and Hemolysis assay can be carried out in order to evaluate the safety of the synthesized nanoparticles.

Different Characterization techniques for nanomaterials

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

DLS technique is used to measure the hydrodynamic diameter of the nanoparticles. It uses theoretical relations measuring the hydrodynamic quantitative values of rotational and translational diffusion coefficients corresponding to the shapes and sizes of particles (Pecora *et al.*, 2013).

The polydispersity index indicates the broadness of the particle size distribution in the form of homogeneity and heterogeneity of the particle size distribution. A particle size distribution with

PDI less than 0.1 indicates a homogenous population while a value greater than 0.3 indicates a heterogeneous population of particles.

Zeta potential

The zeta potential gives information about the surface charge of the nanoparticles. Basically, zeta potential is the measurement of the electrophoretic mobility of the suspended particles. Under an applied electric field, the velocity of the charged particle in a medium is measured using a laser. The nanoparticles having zeta potential greater than +25mV and less than -25mV show greater stability and less agglomeration not allowing Van der Waals forces to cause the attraction between the particles leading to the aggregation of nanoparticles. The zeta potential of bilirubin nanoparticles was ranging between -11 to -16mV indicating good stability and less agglomeration of nanoparticles (Kamothi *et al.*, 2022).

Encapsulation efficiency

Encapsulation efficiency is calculated when a nanocarrier is used to encapsulate any compound. The encapsulation efficiency indicates the nanocarrier's ability to successfully encapsulate a compound and is indicated in the form of a percentage.

Powder X ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD is a technique used to determine the lattice structure of a crystalline substance providing information about the unit cell dimensions, bond angles, chemical composition and crystallographic structure of natural and synthetic materials. The XRD is based on the principle of constructive interference of the X-rays and the nanoparticulate system.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

TEM is done to produce a two-dimensional image of the nanoparticles using a beam of electrons that projects through the sample and produces an image on a phosphorescent screen. TEM gives information about the morphology and size of the nanoparticles. Additionally, the agglomeration/aggregation of the nanoparticles can be detected.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SEM has a high-resolution imaging power and uses electromagnetic and electrostatic lenses to produce images of nanoparticles (Goldstein *et al.*, 2013). SEM produces a three-dimensional image in which first beam of electron scans the surface of the specimen to generate secondary electrons which are then detected by the sensor to produce the image.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

AFM can be used to examine both conducting and nonconducting materials, and provide a three-dimensional and topographical image of the specimen (Allison *et al.*, 2010). The generation

of a picture via AFM is dependent on the measurement of extremely small forces on the sample's particles, which can be as small as single atoms.

UV-Visible spectroscopy

A method frequently used to characterize nanoparticles is UV-vis spectroscopy. This method makes it possible to measure the surface plasmon resonance and verify the synthesis of nanoparticles. This process can reveal details regarding the size, stability, and aggregation of the nanoparticles (Patra and Baek, 2014). UV-Visible spectra also give information about the storage stability of nano formulation.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

For the surface characterization of nanoparticles, FTIR is a particularly flexible method. In addition to identifying the reactive surface sites that cause surface reactivity, it is possible to determine the chemical composition of the nanoparticles under specified conditions (Baraton and Merhari, 2007). FTIR produces specific spectral bands corresponding to the functional groups which is used to know whether there is any conjugation between the nanocarrier and biomolecule (Lin *et al.*, 2014).

Safety evaluation of nanomaterials

The safety evaluation of nanomaterials is can be divided into an *in vitro* and *in vivo* assessment.

***In vitro* assessment methods**

Proliferation assay

By evaluating the metabolically active cells, this assay measures cellular metabolism. The most used tetrazolium salt for evaluating the toxicity of nanoparticles *in vitro* is 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) (Sayes *et al.*, 2007).

Apoptosis assay

There are various techniques for measuring apoptosis. These include the TdT-mediated dUTP-biotin nick end labelling (TUNEL) assay, the Comet assay, the Annexin-V assay (Liang and Clarke, 2001), and the examination of morphological alterations. The endonuclease cleavage products of apoptosis are visualized using the DNA laddering technique. It is simple to distinguish between necrotic and apoptotic types of cell death using agarose gel electrophoresis. Toxicology assessments frequently use the cell death markers annexin-V and propidium iodide (PI). The externalization of the plasma membrane is shown by an increase in fluorescence of Annexin-V's when it binds to phosphatidylserine. The activation of the caspase-dependent mechanism results in this externalization of the plasma membrane.

Necrosis assay

Necrosis, which is frequently used to assess the viability of the cells, is determined by the

membrane's integrity. Neutral Red and Trypan Blue are two dyes that can be taken up by membranes to determine their integrity (Huang *et al.*, 2004; Monteiro-Riviere *et al.*, 2009). Estimating various enzymes, such as lipid peroxidase, reduced glutathione, catalase, superoxide dismutase, and glutathione reductase can be used to evaluate oxidative stress.

***In vivo* assessment methods**

Typically, mice and rats are used as animal models for *in vivo* toxicity testing. Hematology, serum chemistry, biodistribution, clearance, and histopathology are some of the approaches used to evaluate *in vivo* toxicity. Biodistribution studies look at the path that nanoparticles take to reach the tissue or organ. Radiolabels are used to detect nanoparticles in dead or living animals (Jain *et al.*, 2008). Examining the excretion and metabolism of nanoparticles at different times following exposure is how clearance of nanoparticles is accomplished. Examining changes in serum chemistry and cell type following nanoparticle exposure is another technique for determining *in vivo* toxicity. The level of toxicity caused by a nanoparticle is determined by the histopathology of the exposed cell, tissue, or organ following exposure.

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